

analysis the four groups of people have been detected: with cachexy – 8.90 %; with overweight – 31.10 %; with obesity – 31.10 %; with normal values – 28.90 %. The following function data have been studied: level cognition functions, ability to care for himself and hand grip strength. BMI values in men (25.64 ± 4.69) and women (27.10 ± 2.01) had no statistical differences ($P = 0.529$). However a statistical difference between men and women due to level of hand grip strength and endurance of people after 80 years has been exists. Thus hand grip strength does not correlate with BMI at all respondents. It is revealed, direct correlation dependence between BMI values and level cognitive functions ($r = 0.4682$, $P = 0.001$), ability to care for himself ($r = 0.4681$, $P = 0.001$) in the elderly subjects after 80 years. Thus, it was found that elderly people with good functional status has some excess of BMI values controversies to optimum level recommended by experts of nutrition. The revealed phenomenon, probably, reflects interrelation of the main metabolism with the functional capacity level of elderly persons.

CONTROVERSIES IN BODY MASS INDEX AND HUMAN CAPACITY IN AGING

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Numerous researches recommend of normal values of body mass index (BMI) for adult population 18.5 – 25.0 kg/m². The purpose of our research was to study interrelation of functionality and BMI at people after 80 years. It was investigated 45 persons who do not have gastrointestinal problems and cancer at the age of 80 – 94 years: 8 men and 37 women. According to result of the data

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**ABSTRACTS
OF ORAL PRESENTATIONS**

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**The 1st International Congress on Controversies in Longevity, Health and Aging (COLONGy)
Barcelona, Spain, June 24-27, 2010**

Saturday, June 26th, 2010

<p>09:00-10:30</p> <p><i>Capsule:</i></p> <p>Chairpersons:</p> <p>09:00-09:30</p> <p>09:30-10:15</p> <p>10:15-10:30</p>	<p>Parallel Session: New concepts in dementia</p> <p><i>Cognitive disorders such as Alzheimer's disease are the most distressing conditions of aging. Some cognitive impairment can be detected early and can be treated with cognitive exercise and by drugs. Should we start the treatment as soon as early changes are detected?</i></p> <p>A. Korczyn, Israel, J. Kulisevsky, Spain</p> <p>Is vascular cognitive impairment a useful concept? A. Korczyn, Israel</p> <p>DEBATE: The top 10 modifiable risk factors for dementia: Truth or fiction? Truth: D. Gustafson, Sweden Fiction: J. Luchsinger, USA</p> <p>Discussion</p>	<p>09:00-09:45</p> <p><i>Capsule:</i></p> <p>Chairperson:</p> <p>09:00-09:45</p> <p>09:45-10:30</p> <p><i>Capsule:</i></p> <p>Chairperson:</p> <p>09:45-10:30</p>	<p>Parallel Session: Treatment of overactive bladder</p> <p><i>Overactive bladder and urge incontinence prevalence increase in old age. Antimuscarinic drugs are the first line therapy</i></p> <p>E. Topinkova, Czech Republic</p> <p>DEBATE: Do we have evidence of antimuscarinics efficacy in old age? Is there a clinically significant risk of treatment? Efficacy of antimuscarinics on OAB symptoms E. Topinkova, Czech Republic Anticholinergic burden and risk of antimuscarinic drugs in older person patients and in the cognitively impaired A.Wagg, UK</p> <p>Parallel Session: Clinical pharmacology in the elderly</p> <p><i>The elderly are the main consumers of drugs. With the physiological changes in aging, the risk of side-effects is increased – what is the optimal amount of drugs that the older patient can benefit from with the least harm involved?</i></p> <p>G. Gambassi, Italy</p> <p>DEBATE: The benefits and the burden of drugs in older person patients Controversies in geriatric polypharmacy: Does drug withdrawal prolong life? D. Garfinkel, Israel Potential of beneficial drugs (polypill) G. Onder, Italy</p>
<p>10:30-11:00</p>	<p>Coffee break</p>		
<p>11:00-13:00</p> <p><i>Capsule:</i></p> <p>Chairpersons:</p> <p>11:00-11:45</p>	<p>Parallel Session: Hormone replacement therapy in the female</p> <p><i>Over the last 50 years significant experience has been gathered in Hormone Replacement therapy for women of different ages. With great influence on the quality of life as well as certain changes in the prevalence of diseases, are the benefits worth the risks?</i></p> <p>Z. Shoham, Israel; K. Biberoglu, Turkey</p> <p>DEBATE: Management of menopause Should menopause be declared as a pathological state and therefore deserve treatment? Z. Shoham, Israel No treatment is needed during menopause in asymptomatic women K. Biberoglu, Turkey</p>	<p>11:00-12:15</p> <p><i>Capsule:</i></p> <p>Chairperson:</p> <p>11:00-11:50</p> <p>11:50-12:15</p>	<p>Parallel Session: Growth hormone in older persons</p> <p><i>Growth Hormone deficiency leads to the same signs and symptoms as aging. Can we use it to modulate the aging process?</i></p> <p>V. Khavinson, Russia</p> <p>DEBATE: The use of growth hormone in older persons: Cancer risk, premature death, or life extending and anti-cancer effects? Pro: T. Hertoghe, Belgium Con: A. Chaturvedi, India/USA</p> <p>Effects of Hormone Therapy on Depressive symptoms in Women with Alzheimer's disease: A. Valen-Sendstad, Norway</p>

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<p>11:45-12:00</p> <p>12:00-12:15</p> <p>12:15-12:30</p> <p>12:30-12:40</p> <p>12:40-12:50</p> <p>12:50-13:00</p>	<p>Estrogen does not increase breast cancer risk in a way we need to worry about: HRT and breast cancer. Pros and cons G. Kopernik, Israel</p> <p>Does testosterone treatment improve outcome in older age? Pros and cons G. Corona, Italy</p> <p>Can testosterone play a role in the worldwide epidemic of obesity? F. Saad, Germany</p> <p>Controversies in body mass index and human capacity in aging O. Tomarevska, Ukraine</p> <p>Free androgen index and anthropometry, physical performance measures, health-related quality of life, psychological incident, falls and fractures in 1488 older men aged 65 years and over: A 4-year prospective study J. Woo, Hong Kong</p> <p>Panax ginseng enlivens testicular function in old rats S.K. Kim, South Korea</p>	<p>12:15-13:00 <i>Capsule:</i></p> <p>Chairpersons:</p> <p>12:15-12:25</p> <p>12:25-12:40</p> <p>12:40-12:50</p> <p>12:50-13:00</p>	<p>Parallel Session: Sleeping disorders <i>Sleeping disorders are very common in older persons. Drug side effects are very prevalent. How can we optimally manage these disorders which influence the quality of life of the patient as well as his environment?</i> A. Milicevic Kalasic, Serbia; I. Haimov, Israel</p> <p>Use of alternative medicine for sleeping disorders W. Winit-Watjana, UK</p> <p>Use of drugs Y. Berner, Israel</p> <p>Behavior of cancer in the aged implies a specific therapeutic approach J. Leibovici, Israel</p> <p>Transcriptional biomarkers of age and their modulations by dietary interventions J. Barger, USA</p>
<p>13:00-14:00</p>	<p>Lunch break</p>		
<p>14:00-15:30</p> <p><i>Capsule:</i></p> <p>Moderator:</p> <p>14:00-15:30</p>	<p>Parallel Session: Can we treat Sarcopenia in older persons? <i>Loss of muscle mass is common in the older persons especially during health problems. With nutritional supplements and manipulation, can we prevent it or at least reduce its rate during active life and during acute active disease?</i> C. Leeuwenburgh, USA</p> <p>DEBATE: Can we treat Sarcopenia in older persons? Pro: Sarcopenia of older persons is a reversible and treatable condition and intervention may decrease frailty in older persons T. Manini, USA Con: Sarcopenia of older persons is primarily an intrinsic process J. Bauer, Germany</p> <p>Summary: C. Leeuwenburgh, USA</p>	<p>14:00-14:45 <i>Capsule:</i></p> <p>Chairpersons:</p> <p>14:00-14:45</p> <p>14:45-15:30 <i>Capsule:</i></p> <p>Chairperson:</p>	<p>Parallel Session: Cerebral vascular disease in older persons <i>Treatment with streptokinase becomes the "state of the art" treatment of thromboembolic cerebral events. It is an expensive treatment that needs massive infrastructure. It has to be performed in the first hours. Elderly vasculature has certain features that sometimes may increase the risk</i> T. Grodzicki, Poland, A. Korczyn, Israel</p> <p>DEBATE: Patients over 80 years of age should be given the same secondary stroke prophylaxis as those under 80 Pro: D. Russell, Norway Con: N. Bornstein, Israel</p> <p>Parallel Session: Treatment of atrial fibrillation in older persons <i>Atrial fibrillation increases with age and is responsible for many medical problems. Nevertheless, its treatment is sometimes futile and sometimes increases the risk of complications in older persons. It raises the question of whether to use anti-coagulation in order to decrease the complications from atrial fibrillation and the influence of medical treatment on the health of the patient with atrial fibrillation</i> Y. Berner, Israel</p>